

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 30

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 30

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 30:0 A Psalm; a Song at the Dedication of the House. <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p>1 מְזִמּוֹר שִׁיר־תְּנַכַּת הַבַּיִת לְדָוִד : 2 אֲרוּמְמֶנָּה יְהוָה כִּי דָלִיתָנִי וְלֹא־שָׁמַחַתְּ אֵיבֵי לִי : 3 יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי שְׁנַעַתִּי אֲלֵיךָ וַתִּרְפָּאֵנִי : 4 יְהוָה הֶעֱלִיתָ מִן־שָׂאוֹל נַפְשִׁי חַיִּיתָנִי מִיַּזְרֵי־[מ] [יְרֵדִי]־בְּוֹר : 5 וַפְּרֹו לִיהוָה חֲסִידָיו וְהוֹדוּ לְיֹצֵר קִדְשׁוֹ : 6 כִּי רָגַע וּבְאִפְו־תֵּיִם בְּרָצוֹנֹו בְּעָרֵב יָלִין כְּכִי וְלִכְקֹר רָנָה : 7 וְאֲנִי אֲמַרְתִּי בְשִׁלְוִי בַל־אֲמוּט לְעוֹלָם : 8 יְהוָה בְּרָצוֹנֶךָ הֶעֱמַדְתָּה לְהַרְרִי עַו הַסְתַּרְתָּ פָּנֶיךָ תָּנִיתִי נִבְהַל : 9 אֲלֵיךָ יְהוָה אֶקְרָא וְאֶל־אֲדֹנָי אֶתְחַנֵּן : 10 מֵה־ בְּצַע בְּדָמַי בְּרִדְתִּי אֶל־שַׁחַת הַיּוֹדֵךָ עָפָר תִּגִּיד אֲמַתְּךָ : 11 שְׁמַע־יְהוָה וְחַנּוּנִי יְהוָה הִיחֶה־עֵנֶךָ לִי : 12 הַפְּכֶתָ מִסִּפְדִּי לְמַחֹל לִי פִתַּחְתָּ שִׁקִּי וְהִאֲזַנְתִּי שָׁמַחְתָּ : 13 לְמַעַן אִזְמַרְךָ כְּבוֹד וְלֹא יָדָם יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי לְעוֹלָם אֲוֹדֶךָ :</p>
<p>Psa. 30:1 I will ^aextol You, O LORD, for You have ^blifted me up, And have not let my ^cenemies rejoice over me.</p>	
<p>² O LORD my God, I ^acried to You for help, and You ^bhealed me.</p>	
<p>³ O LORD, You have ^abrought up my soul from ¹Sheol; You have kept me alive, ²that I would not ^bgo down to the pit.</p>	
<p>⁴ ^a"Sing praise to the LORD, you ^bHis godly ones, And ^cgive thanks to His holy ^{1d}name.</p>	
<p>⁵ For ^aHis anger is but for a moment, His ^bfavor is for a lifetime; Weeping may ^clast for the night, But a shout of joy <i>comes</i> in the morning.</p>	
<p>Psa. 30:6 Now as for me, I said in my prosperity, "I will ^anever be moved."</p>	
<p>⁷ O LORD, by Your favor You have made my mountain to stand strong; You ^ahid Your face, I was dismayed.</p>	
<p>⁸ To You, O LORD, I called, And to the Lord I made supplication:</p>	

⁹ "What profit is there in my blood,
if I ^ago down to the pit?

Will the ^bdust praise You? Will it
declare Your faithfulness?

Psa. 30:10 "^aHear, O LORD, and be
gracious to me;

O LORD, be my ^bhelper."

¹¹ You have turned for me ^amy
mourning into dancing;

You have ^bloosed my sackcloth
and girded me with ^cgladness,

¹² That *my* ^{1a}soul may sing praise to
You and not be silent.

O LORD my God, I will ^bgive
thanks to You forever.

References

<p>Psalm 30:1 ^aPs 118:28; 145:1 ^bPs 3:3 ^cPs 25:2; 35:19, 24</p> <p>Psalm 30:2 ^aPs 88:13 ^bPs 6:2; 103:3; Is 53:5</p> <p>Psalm 30:3 ¹i.e. the nether world ²Some mss read <i>from among those who go down</i> ^aPs 86:13 ^bPs 28:1</p> <p>Psalm 30:4 ¹Lit <i>memorial</i> ^aPs 149:1 ^bPs 50:5 ^cPs 97:12 ^dEx 3:15; Ps 135:13; Hos 12:5</p> <p>Psalm 30:5 ^aPs 103:9; Is 26:20; 54:7, 8 ^bPs 118:1 ^cPs 126:5; 2 Cor 4:17</p> <p>Psalm 30:6 ^aPs 10:6; 62:2, 6</p> <p>Psalm 30:7 ^aDeut 31:17; Ps 104:29; 143:7</p> <p>Psalm 30:9 ^aPs 28:1 ^bPs 6:5</p>	<p>Psalm 30:10 ^aPs 4:1; 27:7 ^bPs 27:9; 54:4</p> <p>Psalm 30:11 ^aEccl 3:4; Jer 31:4, 13 ^bIs 20:2 ^cPs 4:7</p> <p>Psalm 30:12 ¹Lit <i>glory</i> ^aPs 16:9; 57:8; 108:1 ^bPs 44:8</p>
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Targum

Psa. 30:1 A praise song for the dedication of the sanctuary. Of David. ² I will praise you, O LORD, for you made me stand erect, and did not let my enemies rejoice over me. ³ O LORD my God, I prayed in your presence and you healed me. ⁴ O LORD, you raised my soul out of Sheol; you preserved me from going down to the pit. ⁵ Sing praise in the LORD's presence, you his devotees; and give thanks at the invocation of his holy one. ⁶ For his anger is but a moment; eternal life is his good pleasure. In the evening one goes to bed in tears, but in the morning one rises in praise. ⁷ And I said when I dwelt in trust, I will never be shaken. ⁸ O LORD, by your will you prepared the mighty mountains; you removed your presence, I became afraid. ⁹ In your presence, O LORD, I will cry out; and to you, O my God, I will pray. ¹⁰ <And I said,> What profit is there in my blood, when I descend to the grave? Can those who descend to the dust praise you? Will they tell of your faithfulness? ¹¹ Accept, O LORD, my prayer, and have mercy on me; O LORD, be my helper. ¹² You turned my lament into my celebration; you loosened my sackcloth and girded me with joy. ¹³ Because the nobles of the world will give you praise and not be silent, O LORD my God, I [too] will give you praise.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm was written for the dedication of Solomon's Temple in Jerusalem. It is reserved today for occasions of innovation. It is also used for the inauguration of a time of daily prayers of praise. The Psalm does not say one word about the Temple. It does seem odd that this Psalm was about the consecration of the Temple to the LORD when it never mentions it. Instead, this Psalm consists of a lifetime of experiences attesting to healing, deliverance, trials, and bliss.

Superscript

The superscript for this Psalm is verse one in Hebrew and Targum. It is called a Psalm of David even though it was written for the dedication of the House of the LORD. It was David who gave his son Solomon the instructions and directions to build and furnish the Temple. David also collected the materials that Solomon needed for the project.

A Psalm, a song of the dedication of the Temple, by David

Verse One

דָּלִיתָנִי (deleetanee) – means "lifted." This word's meaning is derived from the word דָּלָה (dala). This word means to draw water. The spiritual awareness of this word is to lift an object from the depths towards oneself and keep the object hanging suspended over that depth. The inference is that *deleetanee* accurately describes the uniqueness of

David's position. Any person who relies entirely upon the LORD's guidance and direction is drawn up like water by the LORD. People whom the LORD do not draw up rely on some prop on earth below their feet. David's support was not from below but rather from above, that is, from the LORD. There is nothing on earth that can uphold or support us.

David's enemies tried to cast him into the depths of despair where he could have died. The LORD lifted him up above his enemies, and David was triumphant.

I extol You, LORD, for you have raised me from the depths and have not allowed my enemies to rejoice by their attempts to pull me into the depths.

Verse two and three

There was a point in David's life that he felt that he was being taken into Sheol (the grave), and the LORD raised him back to health.

O LORD, my God, I cried out to you, and you healed me.

O LORD, you brought my soul up from the grave; You kept me alive, that I would not go into the tomb.

Verse four

The demonstrations of the LORD's greatness led to the House of the LORD in Jerusalem. It represented a charge to all people to give of themselves to the LORD with complete devotion of self.

חֲסִידַי (chaseedan) – means "holy one, saint." The Temple calls all saints of the LORD to draw near with thoughts and emotions of joyous exaltation. The scene at the Temple was one of serenity and joy.

All saints sing to the LORD and thanks to His holy Name.

Verse five

The ways of the LORD are nothing but gifts of life and joy.

For the LORD's anger is but for a moment, weeping will tarry for the night, and joy will come in the morning.

Verse six to eleven

These verses describe a serious moment in David's difficult life. It was an incident that eventually was resolved with gladness. It was a blissful gift of providence. The suffering that David experienced convinced him to stay with the LORD. That meant that he placed his hopes and trust in the LORD. He received the LORD's help then and throughout his entire life.

Now, as for me, I said in my prosperity, "I will never be moved."

O LORD, by Your favor, You have made my mountain to stand firm;

You hid Your face, I was dismayed.

To You, O LORD, I called, And to the Lord I made supplication:

"What profit is there in my blood if I go down to the pit? Will the dust praise You? Will it declare Your faithfulness? "Hear, O LORD, and be gracious to me; O LORD, be my helper."

You have turned for me my mourning into dancing; You have loosed my sackcloth and girded me with gladness.

Verse twelve

Everything we see and touch is a product of the LORD's greatness. It is the mighty force of the LORD that creates and sustains everything.

כְּבוֹד (kavod) – means "glorious or glory." The NASB translates this word as "soul."

The psalmist was not just talking about his soul singing praises to the LORD but rather everything on earth singing. This singing is an acknowledgment by all of creation that the LORD reigns.

Therefore all that is glorious will sing to You, O LORD, I will give you thanks forever.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A Psalm, a song of the dedication of the Temple, by David

I extol You, LORD, for you have raised me from the depths and have not allowed my enemies to rejoice by their attempts to pull me into the depths.

O LORD, my God, I cried out to you, and you healed me.

O LORD, you brought my soul up from the grave; You kept me alive, that I would not go into the tomb.

All saints sing to the LORD and thanks to His holy Name.

For the LORD's anger is but for a moment, weeping will tarry for the night, and joy will come in the morning.

Now, as for me, I said in my prosperity, "I will never be moved."

O LORD, by Your favor, You have made my mountain to stand firm; You hid Your face, I was dismayed.

To You, O LORD, I called, And to the Lord I made supplication:

"What profit is there in my blood if I go down to the pit? Will the dust praise You? Will it declare Your faithfulness? "Hear, O LORD, and be gracious to me; O LORD, be my helper."

You have turned for me my mourning into dancing; You have loosed my sackcloth and girded me with gladness.

Therefore all that is glorious will sing to You, O LORD, I will give you thanks forever.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

